

Milestone: M3.6.1 First release of the Accessible Genome Dashboard available

Lead Participant: VUmc

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Due: 31 Dec 2021

Date Of Completion: 04 Mar 2022

Means of Verification

First insiders look and demo of the dashboard to Astrid Vicente, Juan Arenas, Szymon Bielecki March 4th 2022.

Demonstrations at various meetings amongst which the 1+MG special group meeting April 1st, see also this presentation [Item 1b - 20220401 Dashboard of accessible genomes - Google Presentaties](#)

Old link to that version is not available anymore since we currently are in production. You can access the public version via [B1MG - Maps \(onemilliongenomes.eu\)](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes, due to time consuming effort to arrive at signed sub-contracting software development and maintenance agreement for this task

Project participants & others

The subcontractor Health-RI (Wouter van Stralen, Jesper Peterse)

Astrid Vicente and Szymon Bielecki (EU 1MG survey: data providers)

Juan Arenas (ELIXIR-hub)

Jeroen Belien (task lead)

Various testers (dataset holders, country representatives)

Next action steps

M3.6.2 working towards final release: finishing SOW and processing feedback

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